

Studies on Dithiocarbamates: Part III. Azorhodanines.

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3-Arylrhodanines undergo facile diazo coupling to provide the corresponding 3-aryl-5-arylazorhodanines. Absorption characteristics of these compounds have been recorded; spectral data suggest that the compounds have the azo-structure(II).

Extensive work¹ in the field of dithiocarbamates and related compounds proved to be rewarding in the development of various fungicides and insecticides. As the presence of an azo-moiety frequently confers biocidal properties on a compound, the preparation and characterisation of various azorhodanines are potentially attractive.

Previous work in this field is mainly due to Russian workers^{2,3} who reported a number of 5-arylazorhodanines. Similar preparations from 3-alkylrhodanines are reported in two recent patents⁴. We have therefore extended our previous work³ to the preparation and characterisation of several 3-aryl-5-arylazorhodanines (II) which seem to have not yet been reported.

The high reactivity of the methylene group of rhodanines have been elegantly exploited⁶ in a number of ways. As expected, the rhodanines smoothly reacted with diazonium salts to provide the corresponding azo-derivatives (II) in excellent yields. Ammoniacal dimethyl formamide was found to be the most suitable solvent for running this reaction. In general, the products separated in the course of the reaction and subsequent crystallisation from a suitable solvent afforded yellow to orange coloured compounds (II). Pertinent data are recorded in Table I.

1. Thorn and Ludwig, "The Dithiocarbamates and related compounds", Elsevier Publishing Co., New York, 1962.
2. Grishchuk & Baranov, *Zhur. Obshchei Khim.*, 1958, 28, 896 ; 1959, 29, 3329.
3. Grishchuk & Baranov, *Zh. Organ Khim.*, 1965, 1, 762.
4. Belg. Pat., 637, 282 (1964), *Chem. Abst.*, 1965, 62, 8949; *Neth. Appl.*, 1964, 294, 911; *Chem. Abst.*, 1965, 63, 11268.
5. Talukdar, *Ind. J. Appl. Chem.*, 1965, 28, 197.
6. Brown, *Chem. Revs.*, 1961, 61, 463.

TABLE I

Physical data on Azorhodanines (II).

Sl. No.	R' = H R =	M.P., °C (% Yield)	Crystallising Solvent	R _f	Molecular Formula	Found			Required		
						C	H	N%	C	H	N%
1.	Cyclohexyl	190 (81)	Benzene	0.78	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS ₂	—	—	12.88	—	—	13.16
2.	Benzyl	207 (80)	Acetone- Benzene	0.60	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ OS ₂	58.48	4.10	—	58.72	3.97	—
3.	Phenyl	220-21 (88)	"	0.55	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ OS ₂	—	—	13.28	—	—	13.42
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	214-15 (80)	Benzene	0.52	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ OS ₂	—	—	12.90	—	—	12.84
5.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	188-89 (75)	"	0.51	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ OS ₂	—	—	12.90	—	—	12.84
6.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxy- phenyl	258-59d(75)	Acetone- Benzene	0.27	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	—	—	12.84	—	—	12.76
7.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	206-7 (84)	Benzene	0.53	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	56.83	4.58	—	57.14	4.20	—
8.	<i>p</i> -Chloro- phenyl	227d (82)	Acetone	0.66	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ OS ₂	51.62	3.10	—	51.79	2.88	—
9.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	234d(80)	Benzene	0.56	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ BrN ₃ OS ₂	45.62	2.59	—	45.92	2.55	—
10.	3'-Pyridyl	241-42d(90)	Acetone	0.30	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₄ OS ₂	52.99	3.44	—	53.50	3.18	—
11.	<i>N</i> -Piperidino	178-79(90)	Methanol	0.61	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ OS ₂	52.84	5.36	—	52.50	5.00	—
12.	<i>N</i> -Morpholino	245-46d(90)	Methanol	0.46	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	48.22	4.33	—	48.45	4.35	—
13.	Phenyl ^a	181-2 (81)	Acetone	0.45	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	57.08	4.51	—	57.14	4.20	—
14.	Phenyl ^b	243-44 d(80)	Acetone- Benzene	0.47	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	50.56	2.96	—	50.28	2.79	—

(a) R' = *p*-Ethoxy(b) R' = *p*-Nitro

In this connection it is pertinent to recall Japp-Klingemann' reaction. Bearing in mind the facile azo-hydrazo isomerism, the alternative hydrazone structure (III) for the isolated compounds could not be ruled out. Indeed, Grishchuk and Baranov in one of their communications⁸, assigned hydrazone structure to such derivatives on the basis of chemical degradations. It is obvious that such assignments are of doubtful value in dealing with highly susceptible molecule. Spectral evidence (see next page), on the other hand, unequivocally suggests azo-structure (II) for the isolated compounds. In any event the homogeneity of the products was tested by TLC over silica-gel when each and every compound gave a single spot with characteristic colour and R_f values as noted in Table I.

Examination of Infra red spectra of 1, 2, 3, 7, 9 and 13 of Table I as representative members of the series, did not reveal any band around 3300 cm.⁻¹ (-NH-), but the presence of band around 1720(-CO-)⁸, 1540 (-N=N-)⁹ and 1460⁸ (>N-C=S) cm.⁻¹ are clear indications⁸ of structure (II). Further, the presence of a double bond at C₅ is known⁸ to exert bathochromic shift on carbonyl absorption band and this is evidently lacking in the present instances. A typical absorption curve is shown in fig. 1.

All these compounds gave similar absorption curves both in the visible and ultraviolet regions suggesting similarity in their structural pattern. The highly intense and symmetrical band around 416 mμ in chloroform solution shows a red shift (≈ 5 mμ) in ethanolic solution. This is evidently due to resonance interaction between -N=N- and the aryl

7. Heath-Brown and Philpott, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 7185.8. Brown *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, 24, 1056; Thorn, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1960, 38, 1439.

9. Bellamy, "The Infra-red spectra of complex Molecules", Methuen & Co., London, 1958.

group. This is corroborated by considerable bathochromic shift of this band in the case of compound no. 13 (Table I) and the lack of significant hypsochromic shift for compound no. 14 (Table I) suggests increased resonance interaction due to NO_2 group. Electronic transition involved in this process is the usual $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ type.

FIG. 1. Infra red spectrum of 3-cyclohexyl-1-phenyl-azorhodanine in pot. bromide disc.

TABLE II

Absorption Spectra of Azorhodanines

Sl. No.	Compd (II) R' = H and R =	Ultraviolet spectra				Infra red Spectra		
		$\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{CHCl}_3}$		$\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$		Cm^{-1}		
		μ	ϵ_{max}	μ	ϵ_{max}	-CO-	-N=N-	>N-C=S
1.	Cyclohexyl	302	11,640	241	8660	1709	1534	1479
		416	29,930	298-99	10,420			
2.	Benzyl	298	12,230	240	9690	1720	1550	1465
		416	33,180	293	9570			
3.	Phenyl	298-301	10,860	238	9850	1718	1534	1481
		416	27,870	299-301	8480			
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl			235 sh*	13,330			
		300	9980	299	9930			
5.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	416	28,740	422	28,430			
		264	8220	240-41	10,760			
6.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	300	11,750	296-97	10,090			
		416	30,850	422	30,910			
				235	15,680			
				301-302	10,420			
				422	31,490			

TABLE II (contd.)

Sl. No.	Compd(II) R' = H and R =	Ultraviolet spectra				Infra red Spectra		
		λ_{CHCl_3} max		λ_{EtOH} max		Cm^{-1}		
		m μ	ϵ_{max}	m μ	ϵ_{max}	-CO-	-N=N-	>N-C=S
7.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	299-300	11,660	236	17,290	1730	1545	1460
		416	30,870	291	10,200			
8.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl			220 sh*	17,550			
		302	11,450	296-97	8860			
		418	29,840	422	27,790			
9.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl			225 sh*	15,210	1730	1550	1465
		301	12,230	296	9190			
		420	31,560	422	25,620			
10.	3'-Pyridyl			—				
		301	9500	289-93	9959			
		426	27,510	426	21,290			
11.	<i>N</i> -Piperidino			241	9150			
		295-99	8020	290-93	8770			
		416	25,660	420	28,890			
12.	<i>N</i> -Morpholino			240	9490			
		294	9950	290-93	9410			
		416	27,860	420	30,510			
13.	Phenyl ^a			236	11,450	1720	1545	1460
		305	11,660	301-04	11,760			
		442	23,850	446	27,460			
14.	Phenyl ^b			302	55,70			
		319-20	8840	311-13	5770			
		418	45,900	424	30,880			
				560	5070			

* Approximate band positions for shoulders

(a) R' = *p*-Ethoxy, (b) R' = *p*-Nitro

In the ultraviolet region, another wide and strong band was noted around 300 m μ in chloroform and this did not show any clear cut change in ethanolic solution. However, in many cases, there were indications of the presence of more than one band in chloroform solution.

Rhodanines are known^{4,5} to exhibit two fairly strong bands around 250 m μ and 290 m μ . But in the case of azo-derivatives, the 250 m μ band of the parent rhodanines exhibited profound hypsochromic shift. The magnitude of the blue shift, as clearly shown in fig. 2, in many cases was to such an extent that the band almost disappeared from the measurable region. Although no definite correlation could be established, it is reasonable to suggest that this phenomenon must in some way be associated with the aryl-azo group at C₃. It is conceivable that a *cis*-arrangement of rhodanyl and aryl groups around -N=N- would bring the aryl group sufficiently close to -S- atom to restrict the delocalisation of sulphur electrons. This would account for the observed facts. These

findings are in accord with the previous observations of Janssen¹⁰ who attributed the 250 m μ band to S-conjugation and the 290 m μ band to N-conjugation.

FIG. 2. Ultraviolet Spectra (EtOH) of 3-Phenyl (a), 3-p-Tolyl (b), and 3-p-Bromophenyl-5-phenyl-azorhodanines (c) and 3-phenylrhodanine (d).

Further, the azoderivatives were found to exhibit reversible colour change in acid (yellow) and alkali (pink). However, the colour was more labile in the alkaline medium and this is presumably due to the fission of the rhodanine ring by alkali. This aspect of the problem is under investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL

The compounds recorded in Table I were prepared by the same method, hence a typical preparation is detailed below.

Preparation of 3-Phenyl-5-phenylazorhodanine.—Aniline (2.5 m. mole) was diazotised in the usual way at 0-5° with sodium nitrite (2.5 m. mole) and hydrochloric acid (2.5 ml; 6N). This was added dropwise with agitation to a cold solution (below 5°) of 3-phenyl-

rhodanine in 10 ml. of dimethylformamide. During the course of this addition, pH was maintained around 8 with occasional addition of cold aqueous ammonia solution (10%). After complete addition of diazonium chloride, the deep red mixture was stirred for 30 min. more, filtered and the residue was washed with small quantities of cold water. After air drying, crystallisation of the crude product from acetone-benzene mixture afforded orange-yellow product.

With 3-*o*-tolylrhodanine, the initial coupling product was isolated as an oil which on trituration with 95% ethanol gave the crystalline product.

Using *p*-phenotidine and *p*-nitroaniline in place of aniline in the above preparation, the corresponding azoderivatives (nos. 13, 14 respectively, Table I) were isolated as orange and golden yellow crystals respectively.

Thin layer chromatography (TLC).—The glass plates (20 × 20 cm.) were coated with silica gel (National Chemical Laboratory, Poona) in the usual way. The plates were activated at 120° for 30 min. The spots were developed with 3:1 hexane ethyl acetate mixture (v/v). Characteristic R_f values are shown in Table I.

Absorption spectra.—Infra-red spectra for compound no.1 and 3 (Table I) were determined in potassium bromide disc and those of 2,7,9 and 13 (Table I) were measured in Nujol. Important band positions pertinent to our work are shown in Table II.

Ultraviolet spectra were measured with Hilger UV Speck spectrophotometer, in 1 cm. matched quartz cells.

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